

Masculinity Norms and Subjective Well-Being Among Male Adult Catholics Of Central Deanery, Archdiocese of Nairobi

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the intersection of masculinity norms and subjective well-being among male adult Catholics in the Central Deanery of the Nairobi Archdiocese. The objective of the study was to examine the influence of masculinity norms on the subjective well-being of male adult Catholics. Guided by Social Constructionist and Gender Role Theories, the research employed a mixed-methods convergent parallel design, targeting 1,055 male adults with a sample of 282. Stratified random sampling was used for quantitative data, while qualitative participants were purposively selected. Data collection involved structured Likert-scale questionnaires and semi-structured interviews, with statistical methods including correlation, regression, and ANOVA, alongside thematic analysis for qualitative data. Findings revealed a weak but significant correlation ($r = 0.166, p < 0.01$) between Positive and Negative Affect, suggesting emotional volatility. Norms like Self-Reliance and Emotional Control slightly reduced Positive Affect, whereas Power over Women ($B = 1.214, p = 0.010$) and Playboy ($B = 0.534, p = 0.021$) increased it. The regression model for Positive Affect was statistically significant. No masculinity norm significantly predicted Negative Affect. Positive affect and masculinity norms had a negative correlation. Inter-correlations among masculinity subscales pointed to a cohesive masculinity script.

Key Words: Masculinity norms, Subjective well-being, Male adults, Central Deanery,

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INTRODUCTION

Masculinity norms are defined as a set of societal expectations and rules that guide men on how to behave in society. These norms prescribe traits such as bravery, self-sufficiency, toughness, and emotional strength to maintain societal respect and status (Dutta, 2022). Globally, these norms emphasize independence, dominance, and stoicism while discouraging emotional expression, vulnerability, and help-seeking. For many men across the world, traits like stoicism and self-reliance are idealized, often to the detriment of their subjective well-being (Ronald, 2021). Men who internalize these norms tend to avoid seeking support or expressing distress, which may lead to a decline in their overall life satisfaction and emotional health (Wadley, 2020; Wilson, 2022).

The link between masculinity and subjective well-being is increasingly recognized in global research. Scholars argue that masculinity norms significantly affect men's psychological outcomes and behaviors, including their reluctance to seek support or express emotion (Dutta, 2022). Subjective well-being (SWB), on the other hand, defined as an individual's evaluation of life satisfaction, emotional experiences, and sense of happiness (Diener et al., 2003), is often compromised by these pressures. Men adhering to traditional masculinity may experience reduced SWB due to societal expectations that discourage vulnerability or emotional openness (Wong et al., 2017).

Globally, different cultural contexts shape the way masculinity is defined and experienced. In Western societies, masculinity is often associated with independence, emotional suppression, and achievement (Pietraszkiewicz et al., 2017). In contrast, Eastern societies may emphasize collectivism, family roles, and duty, though the expectation to conform remains equally strong

(Schwartz, 1992). In both cases, deviations from societal norms can lead to reduced SWB. Furthermore, economic instability adds another layer to this experience, as men across the world often associate their worth with their role as financial providers (Pezzini, 2021).

From an African perspective, masculinity is largely shaped by tradition, socio-economic pressures, and collective values. African masculinity often emphasizes the man's role as provider, leader, and protector. Traits like authority, resilience, and responsibility are seen as essential to manhood. While these traits may offer purpose and identity, they can also burden men, especially when traditional provider roles become difficult due to economic constraints, leading to stress, dissatisfaction, and compromised SWB (Tamunomiegbam & Arinze, 2024; Pezzini, 2021). Men in African societies are often expected to provide for extended families, show emotional restraint, and maintain dominance in household leadership (Tift, 2019). Such expectations are deeply embedded in cultural norms, making deviation from these roles a potential source of shame or perceived failure. As a result, many men do not seek emotional or psychological support, fearing they will appear weak or unmanly (Baker, 2019; Gough & Novikova, 2020). This resistance to acknowledging psychological needs contributes to low levels of help-seeking behavior and has a direct impact on their SWB (Ezeugwu & Ojedokun, 2020).

Urbanization and exposure to global ideas around gender equality have led some African men to adopt more progressive masculinity ideals such as emotional openness and shared responsibilities (Silberschmidt, 2011). However, transitioning from traditional to modern masculinity norms presents a challenge. Without adequate support systems, this shift may further compromise men's SWB due to societal and internal conflict (Kaufman, 2021).

In Kenya, masculinity closely mirrors the broader African experience, with strong cultural and societal expectations placed on men to be stoic, emotionally reserved, and primary providers. Young Kenyan boys are often socialized into these roles through formal and informal initiation processes guided by older men (Mahalik et al., 2006). While fulfilling these roles can offer pride and identity, they may also lead to emotional suppression, social isolation, and low SWB when men struggle to meet expectations or internalize failure. Masculinity norms in Kenya continue to affect the lived experience of adult men, particularly in how they approach emotional health and interpersonal relationships. These norms restrict emotional expression and frame help-seeking as a sign of weakness, which not only harms interpersonal relations but also suppresses overall life satisfaction and emotional fulfillment (Ogutu, 2019; Ezeugwu & Ojedokun, 2020).

In the Central Deanery of the Archdiocese of Nairobi, a central administrative and pastoral unit in Kenya's Catholic Church, masculinity is shaped not only by cultural traditions but also by religious teachings. The Catholic Church plays a central role in shaping values, including gender norms, in many Kenyan communities. Here, traditional masculinity is reinforced through both scripture and church culture, which may emphasize stoicism, authority, and service. While Catholic virtues like humility and service can positively influence SWB, rigid interpretations of masculinity may lead to denial, stigmatization, and reluctance to seek support when needed (Sarrasin et al., 2015; Awan, 2023). Despite global and local advancements in promoting mental health awareness, many religious communities, including those within the Central Deanery, continue to reinforce traditional masculinity norms that may hinder men's SWB. The overlap of religious and cultural expectations creates a powerful narrative that discourages men from acknowledging emotional struggles or seeking help.

Thus, investigating masculinity norms and their influence on the subjective well-being of male adult Catholics within the Central Deanery provides critical insight into how these norms operate at the intersection of culture, religion, and individual experience. This study seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the challenges these men face and to inform the development of contextually relevant interventions that promote their subjective well-being within both religious and social frameworks.

Objective: To examine the influence of masculinity norms on the subjective well-being of male adult Catholics.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods research design using a convergent parallel approach to examine the relationship between masculinity norms and subjective well-being among adult male Catholics in the Central Deanery of the Archdiocese of Nairobi. Quantitative and qualitative data were collected concurrently and analyzed separately, with the findings later merged to generate integrated conclusions. This approach enabled a comprehensive understanding by combining the generalizability of quantitative data with the contextual richness of qualitative insights, capturing both patterns and underlying experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Kothari, 2004). Integration of both strands facilitated deeper insights into how masculinity norms affect well-being, including cultural and interpersonal factors shaping male identity and emotional health (Creswell, 2007).

The study was situated in the Central Deanery, a densely populated, ethnically diverse urban area in Nairobi County, Kenya. The deanery includes parishes such as Holy Family Minor Basilica, St.

Paul's Chapel Parish, St. Peter Clavers Parish, Our Lady Queen of Peace, St Francis Xavier, St Catherine of Alexandria south C and Don Bosco Upper Hill (Archdiocese of Nairobi [ADN, 2023]). Reflecting Nairobi's cosmopolitan character, the population comprises individuals from various ethnicities, age groups, and socio-economic strata, many of whom actively engage in parish life. This multicultural and religious setting offers a valuable context for examining masculinity as shaped by faith, community participation, and social expectations. The area also benefits from devolved healthcare and local governance systems, enhancing service accessibility and informing local perspectives on well-being (Kimathi, 2017).

The target population consisted of adult male Catholics aged 18 and above who were active members of parishes within the deanery. According to the 2024 Archdiocesan census, there were 1,055 eligible participants (ADN, 2024). The study aimed for demographic diversity across age, marital status, educational attainment, employment type (formal, informal, or retired), and socio-economic background. All participants were regularly involved in parish-based groups such as prayer cells or community service, which contribute to the construction and reinforcement of masculine identity within the Catholic context. This diversity allowed for exploration of how masculinity intersects with socio-cultural and religious factors to influence well-being.

A stratified random sampling technique was used to ensure balanced representation across the seven parishes and key demographic variables. Each parish provided lists of eligible adult male members, which served as the sampling frames. Within each stratum (based on age and marital status), participants were randomly selected using a lottery method (Creswell & Creswell, 2018; Mesa et al., 2016). The quantitative sample size was determined using Cochran's formula for a

finite population ($N = 1,055$), resulting in a sample of 282 participants, with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. From this group, a purposive subsample of 20 participants was drawn for qualitative interviews to ensure depth and variation in experiences (Palinkas et al., 2015; Kothari, 2004).

Quantitative data was collected using structured questionnaires that incorporated two standardized instruments. The Conformity to Masculine Norms Inventory (CMNI-46) was used to assess adherence to traditional and contemporary masculine ideologies (Mahalik et al., 2003). Subjective well-being was measured using the Positive and Negative Affect Schedule (PANAS), which evaluates emotional states across positive and negative dimensions (Watson et al., 1988). Data collection occurred over a one-month period during parish gatherings, with trained research assistants available to support respondents needing clarification (Kothari, 2004). Data were coded and analyzed using SPSS software to generate inferential statistics.

Qualitative data were obtained through semi-structured interviews with the 20 purposively selected participants. Interviews were conducted privately, lasting between 45 and 60 minutes, and guided by open-ended questions focused on masculinity and well-being (Dougla et al., 2022). This format encouraged participants to share personal narratives and reflect on cultural influences, interpersonal relationships, and religious expectations that shape their understanding of masculinity. The qualitative data provided depth and nuance that contextualized the statistical trends identified in the survey findings.

To ensure instrument validity and cultural appropriateness, pre-testing was conducted with 30 adult male Catholics from Kabete Deanery, a neighboring area demographically similar to the

Central Deanery. Using purposive sampling, the pre-test assessed clarity, flow, and cultural sensitivity of the questionnaire and interview guide (Abey, 2024). Based on feedback, revisions were made to reword ambiguous items, improve sequencing, and ensure language accessibility. Mock interviews were also conducted, further refining the qualitative guide and enhancing the reliability of responses (Hashim et al., 2022; Debbie, 2001).

Ethical considerations were rigorously observed throughout the research process. Participants received full information about the study's aims, procedures, risks, and benefits before providing written informed consent (Yip et al., 2016). Participation was entirely voluntary, and respondents were informed of their right to withdraw at any stage without penalty. Confidentiality was maintained through coded identification, and all data were securely stored with restricted access. The study respected the autonomy and dignity of participants and was particularly attentive to minimizing risks to potentially vulnerable individuals (Resnik, 2020; Fleming, 2018). Ethical clearance was granted by the Institutional Review Board (IRB) prior to fieldwork, and all decisions relating to ethics were transparently documented (Bhandari, 2021; Mirza et al., 2023).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Correlation Analysis

The Pearson Correlation analysis was conducted to assess the strength and direction of the linear relationship between the two continuous variables; masculinity norms and subjective well-being (positive and negative affect) and CMNI-46 and PANAS scores were used in this analysis. The Pearson correlation results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1
The Pearson correlation analysis results

Variable Pair	r	p-value	Significance
P.A – N.A	.166**	.008	Significant (weak positive)
Winning – Emotional Control	.723**	< .001	Strong positive
Winning – Risk Taking	.880**	< .001	Strong positive
Winning – Violence	.948**	< .001	Very strong positive
Winning – Power over Women	.771**	< .001	Strong positive
Winning – Playboy	.952**	< .001	Very strong positive
Winning – Self-reliance	.879**	< .001	Strong positive
Winning – Primacy of Work	.911**	< .001	Strong positive
Emotional Control – Violence	.885**	< .001	Very strong positive
Emotional Control – Power over Women	.976**	< .001	Very strong positive
Self-reliance – Violence	.976**	< .001	Very strong positive
Primacy of Work – Violence	.954**	< .001	Very strong positive
Heterosexual Self-presentation – All	-0.008 to 0.039	> .50	Not significant

The correlation analysis explored the relationships between affective well-being measured by Positive Affect (P.A.) and Negative Affect (N.A.) and various subscales of masculinity norms as defined by the CMNI-46 among 250 adult male Catholics from the Central Deanery of the Archdiocese of Nairobi.

Positive Affect (P.A.) showed a statistically significant but weak positive correlation with Negative Affect (N.A.) ($r = .166, p < .01$), indicating that individuals experiencing more positive emotions might also report some elements of emotional volatility or coexisting negative affect.

This finding echoes Watson, Clark, and Tellegen's (1988) explanation that Positive Affect and

Negative Affect, although often independent, can both be elevated in individuals with heightened emotional reactivity.

When examining the relationship between Positive affect and masculinity norms, the results indicated small and non-significant negative correlations across almost all subscales, including Winning ($r = -.065$), Emotional Control ($r = -.050$), Violence ($r = -.067$), Self-Reliance ($r = -.073$), and Primacy of Work ($r = -.060$). Though not statistically significant, these negative directions suggest that greater conformity to traditional masculine norms may be weakly associated with lower levels of positive emotional well-being. These results, while modest, suggest that greater conformity to traditional masculinity may dampen the experience of positive emotions, likely due to emotional restriction and social isolation. These findings resonate with those of Wester et al. (2007), who documented how emotionally restrictive gender norms contribute to reduced life satisfaction and hinder emotional connection.

This trend aligns with findings from Mahalik et al. (2003) and Wester et al. (2007), who reported that rigid adherence to traditional masculine norms especially norms discouraging emotional expression or emphasizing dominance can reduce an individual's experience of positive affect and overall psychological well-being. Mahalik and colleagues found that men who closely adhered to such norms often suppressed emotional needs, thereby limiting opportunities for positive emotional experiences and social support.

In contrast, Negative Affect (N.A.) showed no significant correlations with any masculinity subscale. All coefficients were small, ranging from $r = -.057$ to $r = .057$, with p-values above .05. These findings suggest that negative emotional states such as distress, irritability, or nervousness

are not directly predicted by adherence to any particular masculine norm within this specific cultural and religious context.

This absence of significant correlations contrasts somewhat with studies conducted in Western contexts. For example, Wester et al. (2007) and O'Neil (2008) found that conformity to norms such as Self-Reliance and Power over Women were significantly associated with psychological distress. The discrepancy could be attributed to cultural and religious factors in the Central Deanery population, where certain masculine norms might be internalized differently or mediated by strong communal and spiritual support systems that buffer emotional distress.

The correlation matrix revealed very strong and statistically significant positive relationships among most masculinity norm subscales. Notably; Winning and Violence ($r = .948^{**}$), Emotional Control and Power over Women ($r = .976^{**}$), Self-Reliance and Violence ($r = .976^{**}$) and Playboy and Winning ($r = .952^{**}$). These high inter- correlations suggest that these norms are not functioning as isolated traits but are deeply interconnected within the masculine identity of this population. For instance, the high correlation between Emotional Control and Power over Women implies that in this context, emotional suppression may be tied to traditional gender dominance roles. Similarly, the strong links between Winning, Playboy behavior, and Violence suggest a cohesive, culturally-influenced ideal of masculinity emphasizing assertiveness, dominance, and sexual conquest. Such interdependence supports findings from Levant et al. (2013), who observed strong structural correlations among masculine norms, particularly in environments where these traits are socially reinforced.

Interestingly, the subscale Heterosexual Self-Presentation showed no significant correlation with either Positive or Negative Affect, and only weak relationships with other masculinity subscales. This suggests that concerns about appearing heterosexual may be less central to emotional well-being or masculine identity in this cultural context. Similar findings were reported by Parent and Moradi (2009), who noted that this particular norm was less predictive of distress or emotional functioning than other dimensions such as Self-Reliance or Power over Women.

The high correlation between Winning and Risk-Taking ($r = .880$), and between Power over Women and Violence ($r = .883$), reveals how men who conform to one rigid norm are more likely to conform to others suggesting a rigid, domino-like masculinity structure.

The overwhelming correlations of Emotional Control with Power over Women ($r = .976$), Violence ($r = .885$), and Self-Reliance ($r = .958$) show how toxic role modeling can entrench rigid behaviors. Yet, as noted by Iwamoto et al. (2010), alternative masculine expressions especially modeled by male authority figures can reshape norms in healthier directions.

High standard deviations in some subscales suggest that there's no uniform experience of masculinity among Catholic men. This diversity of experience could reflect personal, vocational, or cultural differences such as single versus married life, laymen versus clergy, or urban versus rural contexts. Conversely, the low standard deviations in other subscales suggest that certain masculine norms are experienced as near-universal pressures, particularly emotional suppression and the expectation to provide. These findings align with Valkonen and Hänninen (2022), who observed that while expressions of masculinity are contextually shaped, norms like emotional

restraint and the provider role are widely internalized across diverse male populations, often upheld by both secular and religious frameworks.

Regression Analysis

To examine the predictive influence of masculinity norms on subjective well-being among male adult Catholics, two multiple regression analyses were conducted. The first model explored how masculinity norm subscales predicted Negative Affect while the second model examined how masculinity norms predicted Positive Affect. This approach allowed for a nuanced understanding of how specific dimensions of masculine norm adherence impact the emotional components of subjective well-being.

Table 2

Regression Model 1

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.220 ^a	.048	.013	.3067		

ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.145	9	.127	1.352	.211 ^b
	Residual	22.574	240	.094		
	Total	23.719	249			

Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.176	1.054		4.909	.000
	Winning	-.849	.657	-.971	-1.293	.197

Emotional control	-1.557	1.203	-1.574	-1.294	.197
Risk-taking	-.242	.160	-.225	-1.513	.132
Violence	.716	.828	.801	.865	.388
Power over women	.382	.571	.464	.670	.504
playboy	.417	.281	.474	1.485	.139
Self-reliance	.728	.788	.831	.924	.356
Primacy of work	.048	.227	.046	.213	.831
Heterosexual self- presentation	.054	.106	.032	.508	.612

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the predictive influence of various masculine norms (as measured by subscales such as Winning, Emotional Control, Risk Taking, Violence, Power over Women, Playboy, Self-Reliance, Primacy of Work, and Heterosexual Self-Presentation) on Negative Affect.

The model produced an R value of .220, indicating a low positive correlation between the combined predictors and negative affect. The R Square value (.048) shows that only 4.8% of the variance in negative affect is explained by the nine masculine norm subscales included in the model. The adjusted R Square (.013) further suggests that the explanatory power of the model is weak and may not generalize well beyond the sample.

This analysis for Negative Affect, the model was not statistically significant ($F(9, 240) = 1.352$, $p = .211$), and the explained variance was very low ($R^2 = .048$). None of the individual subscales significantly predicted negative affect, although coefficients such as Emotional Control ($B = -1.557$) and Self-Reliance ($B = 0.728$) showed directional relevance. These non-significant results imply that masculine norms, in this sample are poor predictors of psychological distress. This contradicts previous findings from Western studies in studies conducted by Wester et al., (2007)

and O'Neil (2008) but may highlight protective cultural factors, including religious meaning-making and community support systems, that moderate distress even in the face of restrictive norms.

The weak or absent associations between masculinity and negative affect suggest that in religious communities such as the Central Deanery, emotional coping may be buffered by spiritual practices, social roles, and community expectations. This finding aligns with Mahalik et al. (2003), who noted that conformity to certain masculine norms does not uniformly predict negative psychological outcomes, especially when contextual factors such as spirituality, cultural identity, and social support are present to mediate or buffer these effects.

The ANOVA table reveals that the overall regression model was not statistically significant, $F(9, 240) = 1.352$, $p = .211$, indicating that, collectively, the masculine norm subscales do not significantly predict negative affect.

At the coefficients table, none of the individual predictors significantly contributed to the prediction of negative affect at the conventional significance level ($p < .05$): Winning ($B = -0.849$, $p = .197$) and Emotional Control ($B = -1.557$, $p = .197$) showed negative but non-significant associations with negative affect. Risk Taking ($B = -0.242$, $p = .132$) also had a negative and non-significant effect. Violence ($B = 0.716$, $p = .388$), Power over Women ($B = 0.382$, $p = .504$), and Playboy ($B = 0.417$, $p = .139$) had positive but non-significant effects. Self-Reliance ($B = 0.728$, $p = .356$), Primacy of Work ($B = 0.048$, $p = .831$), and Heterosexual Self-Presentation ($B = 0.054$, $p = .612$) similarly showed no significant relationship.

Table 3

Regression Model 2

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.261 ^a	.068	.033	.2518

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.117	9	.124	1.957	.045 ^b
	Residual	15.215	240	.063		
	Total	16.332	249			

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	5.519	.866		6.376	.000
	Winning	-1.023	.539	-1.409	-1.897	.059
	Emotional control	-1.452	.988	-1.770	-1.470	.143
	Risk taking	-.122	.131	-.136	-.926	.355
	Violence	1.062	.680	1.432	1.563	.119
	Power over women	1.214	.469	1.777	2.591	.010
	playboy	.534	.230	.732	2.316	.021
	Self-reliance	-.598	.647	-.824	-.925	.356
	Primacy of work	.041	.187	.047	.220	.826
	Heterosexual self-presentation	-.002	.087	-.001	-.019	.985

A multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the extent to which conformity to traditional masculine norms predicted levels of positive affect among the participants. The nine

masculine norms included as independent variables in the model were: Winning, Emotional Control, Risk Taking, Violence, Power over Women, Playboy, Self-Reliance, Primacy of Work, and Heterosexual Self-Presentation.

The overall regression model was statistically significant, $F(9, 240) = 1.957, p = .045$, indicating that the combination of masculine norms explained a small but significant proportion of the variance in positive affect. The model yielded an R value of .261 and an R Square of .068, suggesting that approximately 6.8% of the variance in positive affect was accounted for by the predictors. However, the Adjusted R Square was .033, indicating that after adjusting for the number of predictors, the model explained only 3.3% of the variance. The standard error of the estimate was .2518.

This basically implies that the regression model for Positive Affect was statistically significant ($F(9, 240) = 1.957, p = .045$), albeit with a modest R^2 value of .068. Two subscales; Power over Women ($B = 1.214, p = .010$) and Playboy ($B = 0.534, p = .021$) were significant predictors. These findings might appear surprising but reflect complex cultural interpretations: for instance, dominance and sexual agency may be linked with feelings of confidence, control, or social affirmation, which are positively associated with affect. This could reflect a contextual valorization of traditional gender roles in which such norms are not just tolerated but admired or rewarded. Connell & Messerschmidt (2005) also demonstrated that similar trends have been observed in non-Western populations where masculine dominance is embedded in social status systems. Yet, the apparent "benefits" of these norms in terms of Positive Affect must be cautiously interpreted, as they may come at the cost of relational or ethical well-being.

Examining the individual predictors, two masculine norms were found to be significant positive predictors of positive affect. The Power over Women norm had a significant positive association with positive affect, $B = 1.214$, $t = 2.591$, $p = .010$. This suggests that higher endorsement of the belief that men should have dominance over women was associated with higher levels of positive affect among respondents. Similarly, the Playboy norm also emerged as a significant predictor, $B = .534$, $t = 2.316$, $p = .021$, indicating that individuals who endorsed behaviors associated with being a playboy reported higher positive affect.

Other masculine norms such as Winning ($p = .059$) and Violence ($p = .119$) showed trends toward significance but did not reach the conventional alpha level of .05. The remaining norms, including Emotional Control, Risk Taking, Self-Reliance, Primacy of Work, and Heterosexual Self-Presentation, did not significantly predict positive affect in the model.

However, the diminished positive affect among those who conform to emotional suppression and self-reliance norms underscores the emotional costs of restrictive gender roles, as supported by Mahalik et al. (2003). At the same time, the positive associations of dominance-related norms with positive affect reveal a tension between emotional well-being and social masculinity scripts, which may perpetuate certain norms despite their long-term psychological consequences.

Overall, the findings suggest that while the masculine norms collectively accounted for a statistically significant but modest portion of the variance in positive affect, only certain norms particularly those related to dominance and sexual freedom were positively associated with emotional well-being in the form of positive affect. This may reflect cultural or contextual dynamics in how masculinity is expressed and experienced among the study population.

CONCLUSION

This study examined how traditional masculinity norms relate to the subjective well-being of adult male Catholics in the Central Deanery. Key traits associated with traditional masculinity such as emotional control, self-reliance, and competitiveness were found to be weakly and negatively associated with positive affect. This suggests that emotional suppression and social isolation may reduce the experience of positive emotions and overall well-being. However, no significant relationship was found between masculinity norms and negative affect, possibly due to the protective influence of spiritual coping and strong community bonds within the religious setting. Regression analysis reinforced the limited predictive power of masculinity norms on negative emotional states. Notably, dominance-oriented traits like “Power over Women” and “Playboy” showed a positive association with positive affect. While this may reflect a sense of affirmation or control in the cultural context studied, it also raises concerns about potential underlying relational or ethical issues.

The findings support Social Constructionist and Gender Role Theories, indicating that masculinity is culturally and socially constructed and often internalized as a moral responsibility. At the same time, the emergence of more emotionally open and spiritually grounded masculinities within the community signals a shift in how gender roles are enacted, revealing the evolving nature of masculinity in religious life.

The study calls for broader research to assess whether these patterns hold across different cultural and geographic contexts. It also highlights the need to explore influences such as education, media, and pastoral guidance, and to include diverse perspectives especially those of women, youth, and clergy in future studies.

In summary, the study reveals the nuanced relationship between masculinity norms, emotional well-being, and religious identity. It emphasizes the importance of continued dialogue and research to encourage healthier, more inclusive expressions of masculinity within faith-based communities.

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